

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.3.3.1: Eutrophication and nutrient deposition

Version: 1

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8036544

Project leader and contributors:

- Vigdis Vandvik (Vigdis.Vandvik@uib.no)

Data curator(s):

- Vigdis Vandvik (Vigdis.Vandvik@uib.no)

- Ryoko Kawakami (r-kawakami@iges.or.jp)

Description

Section 3.3.3.1 assesses the role of eutrophication and nutrient deposition as drivers of biological invasions. The experts conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review consists in the main source of evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Search 2:

Search 3:

Search 4:

Search 5:

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- Search terms:

Search1: TOPIC: ("invasive alien species" OR "invasive species" OR "biotic invasion" OR invasion* OR "alien species" OR "non-native species" OR IASs OR "introduced species" OR "introduced plant*" OR "introduced animal*" OR "alien plant*" OR "alien pest*" OR "alien animal*" OR "invasive plant*" OR "invasive animal*" OR "invasion debt" OR "plant invasion*" OR "animal invasion*" OR "invasion risk" OR "invader*") AND (nitr* OR ammoni* OR eutrophi*)

As above AND ((shift* OR change OR intensification OR intensity OR degrad* OR alterat* OR abandon* OR grazing OR fire OR fishing OR harvest* OR trawl*))

Search 2: TITLE: ("invasive alien species" OR "invasive species" OR "biotic invasion" OR invasion* OR "alien species" OR "non-native species" OR IASs OR "introduced species" OR "introduced plant*" OR "introduced animal*" OR "alien plant*" OR "alien pest*" OR "alien animal*" OR "invasive plant*" OR "invasive animal*" OR "invasion debt" OR "plant invasion*" OR "animal invasion*" OR "invasion risk" OR "invader*") AND TOPIC: (nitr* OR ammoni* OR eutrophi*)

TITLE: (: ("invasive alien species" OR "invasive species" OR "biotic invasion" OR invasion* OR "alien species" OR "non-native species" OR IASs OR "introduced species" OR "introduced plant*" OR "introduced animal*" OR "alien plant*" OR "alien pest*" OR "alien animal*" OR "invasive plant*" OR "invasive animal*" OR "invasion debt" OR "plant invasion*" OR "animal invasion*" OR "invasion risk" OR "invader*") AND (nitr* OR ammoni* OR eutrophi*))

Search 3: TOPIC: (("invasive alien species" OR "invasive species" OR "biotic invasion" OR invasion* OR "alien species" OR "non-native species" OR IASs OR "introduced species" OR "introduced plant*" OR "introduced animal*" OR "alien plant*" OR "alien pest*" OR "alien animal*" OR "invasive plant*" OR "invasive animal*" OR "invasion debt" OR "plant invasion*" OR "animal invasion*" OR "invasion risk" OR "invader*") AND (nitr* OR ammoni* OR eutrophi*)) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Review)

TOPIC: (("invasive alien species" OR "invasive species" OR "biotic invasion" OR invasion* OR "alien species" OR "non-native species" OR IASs OR "introduced species" OR "introduced plant*" OR "introduced animal*" OR "alien plant*" OR "alien pest*" OR "alien animal*" OR "invasive plant*" OR "invasive animal*" OR "invasion debt" OR "plant invasion*" OR "animal invasion*" OR "invasion risk" OR "invader*") AND (nitr* OR ammoni* OR eutrophi*) AND (review))

Search 4: (("invasive alien species" OR "invasive species" OR "biotic invasion" OR invasion* OR "alien species" OR "non-native species" OR IASs OR "introduced species" OR "introduced plant*" OR "introduced animal*" OR "alien plant*" OR "alien pest*" OR "alien animal*" OR "invasive plant*" OR "invasive animal*" OR "invasion debt" OR "plant invasion*" OR "animal invasion*" OR "invasion risk" OR "invader*") AND (nitr* OR ammoni* OR eutrophi*)) AND TOPIC: ((Review OR "Systematic review" OR "Meta-analysis" OR "Metaanalysis" OR "Literature review" OR "Synthesis" OR "Synthesis matrix"))

Search 5: TOPIC: (("invasive alien species" OR "invasive species" OR "biotic invasion" OR invasion* OR "alien species" OR "non-native species" OR IASs OR "introduced species" OR "introduced plant*" OR "introduced animal*" OR "alien plant*" OR "alien pest*" OR "alien animal*" OR "invasive plant*" OR

"invasive animal* OR "invasion debt" OR "plant invasion*" OR "animal invasion*" OR "invasion risk" OR "invader*") AND (nitr* OR ammoni* OR eutrophi*) AND TOPIC: ((Review OR "Systematic review" OR "Meta-analysis" OR "Metaanalysis" OR "Literature review" OR "Synthesis" OR "Synthesis matrix")) AND TOPIC: (Species OR population* OR habitat* OR ecosystem* OR biodiversity OR conservation OR metapopulation* OR "genetic diversity")

("invasive alien species" OR "invasive species" OR "biotic invasion" OR invasion* OR "alien species" OR "non-native species" OR IASs OR "introduced species" OR "introduced plant*" OR "introduced animal*" OR "alien plant*" OR "alien pest*" OR "alien animal*" OR "invasive plant*" OR "invasive animal*" OR "invasion debt" OR "plant invasion*" OR "animal invasion*" OR "invasion risk" OR "invader*") AND (nitr* OR ammoni* OR eutrophi*) AND (Review OR "Systematic review" OR "Meta-analysis" OR "Metaanalysis" OR "Literature review" OR "Synthesis" OR "Synthesis matrix") AND (Species OR population* OR habitat* OR ecosystem* OR biodiversity OR conservation OR metapopulation* OR "genetic diversity")

- **Search engine:** Web of science

- **Date:** December 2020

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result:

37 in total: 7 from Search 1, 8 from Search 2, 3 from Search 3, 7 from Search 4 and 12 from Search 5

Selection criteria:

Search 1, 2 and 5: Searched with above terms, then refined by timespan and relativeness by their title and abstract.

Search 3: Searched with above terms, then refined by document type review. 6 hits if I use "systematic review" instead of "review", of which 4 are relevant at title level and only 3 appear if I also filter by document type review.

Search 4: Searched with above terms, then refined by document type review.

Search 5: Searched with above terms, then used inclusion criteria were that nitrogen was either the independent variable or covariate in the papers included in the review and that some aspect of biodiversity sensu lato was the response variable (but not purely biomass or responses at the cellular level, not medicine), also not crop yield). Several papers were rejected at title for being medicine or cell biology.

At the abstract level: remove the ones where the invasive species is the treatment.

Abstract sift: prioritised actual systematic reviews where the main focus was the effects of nitrogen pollution (not fertiliser) on invasive alien species.

Rejected: not about nitrogen, not about biodiversity (sensu lato), about root nodule formation (rhizobia cells 'invade' the roots), only about control methods, only about traits of invasive species.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 0

Number of papers reviewed: 37 (See Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx)

Fields extracted:

- Publication title
- Year of publication
- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]
- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- Files (code, review templates, etc.):

Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx